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EVALUATION OF LATENT TUBERCULOSIS INFECTION
SCREENING IN THE FIELD

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

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By

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ABSTRACT

The Tuberculin Skin Test (TST), developed in the early 1900s, has been the primary test for Tuberculosis (TB) screening in the Los Angeles County Public Health Department (LACDPH). In 2001, a new test for TB screening, Interferon Gamma Release Assays (IGRA), was developed. Research evidence demonstrates that IGRA testing has improved sensitivity and specificity over TST results and thus, reports fewer false positive results stemming from BCG vaccination or non-tuberculosis mycobacterial infections. In 2013, the department began the implementation of IGRA in the clinic and field setting as evidence based practice for public health nursing. This presentation will report the evaluation of this implementation of IGRA including: (a) usage of IGRA in the field, (b) comparison of latent TB infection rates in 2013 and 2014, and (c) cost analysis including impact of cost for screening with TST and IGRA. The evaluation showed that adoption of evidence based practices varied across settings; barriers need to be identified and addressed in order to ensure implementation that benefits patient outcomes. TB infection rates decreased significantly after IGRA implementation (20% to 13%), likely due to IGRA's increased sensitivity and specificity. The change to IGRA testing resulted in cost saving due to a decrease in LTBI treatment as fewer TB false positive tests occurred. Implications for all local public health departments include considering using IGRA testing in the public health field setting with potential for improvement in identification of true TB infections.

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BACKGROUND

Tuberculosis (TB) remains one of the leading contagious diseases killing 1.3 million people around the world annually (World Health Organization, 2013). As a result, the World Health Organization (WHO) has developed an initiative to eliminate TB that focuses on appropriate screening and treatment for Latent TB Infection (LTBI). The Centers for Disease Control (CDC) has also identified evaluation and treatment completion for contacts as one of their national TB program objectives for 2015 (Centers for Disease Control [CDC], 2014). In 2012 the CDC reported that most populations without risk factors have a 5-10% latent TB infection rate; however populations with risk factors such as the foreign born and the homeless can have a latent TB infection rate of 25 to 30% as well as increased transmission due to congregate living conditions (CDC, 2012). One strategy in these efforts, is to increase LTBI screening among foreign born populations and populations who have poor return rates with an interferon-gamma release assay (IGRA), which is a blood test for tuberculosis as opposed to using a Tuberculin Skin Test (TST) (CDC, 2014).

In an effort to align a large local health department with a high incidence of TB, with screening practices recommended by CDC, the use of IGRA was implemented for both clinic and field testing for the following targeted populations: (a) foreign born, (b) those with poor return rates, and (c) contacts to a TB case or suspect (defined as someone with a positive TB culture or someone with symptoms indicative of TB disease). The purpose of this project is to provide an evaluation of the use of LTBI tests in TB contact investigations in the field through: (a) staff usage of IGRA post policy and documented

staff training, (b) effectiveness comparison of completion of screening for contacts and (c) cost analysis of TST vs. IGRA in the field.

Statement of the Problem

National reporting of TB rates in the United States (U.S.) began in 1953 (CDC, 2014). The CDC (2014) states that for the first time since reporting began the number of new cases in 2012 dropped below 10,000. This incidence rate of 3.2 cases per 100,000 persons represents a 6.1% decrease from 2011; 2012 was the twentieth consecutive year of declining rates (CDC, 2014; Miramontes, Pratt, Price, Navin, & Lo, 2013). Despite this accomplishment, challenges remain in the elimination of TB in the U.S., especially given the high incidence rates among certain populations such as the foreign born (63% of all cases) and the homeless (5.6% of all cases) (CDC, 1991; Miramontes et al., 2013).

In 2013, California reported the highest number of TB cases in the United States with 2,169 new cases and an incidence of 5.7 per 100,000, which is well above the Healthy People 2020 target of 1.0 per 100,000 (California Department of Public Health [CDPH], 2014). In 1992 at the height of the TB epidemic, 5,382 cases were reported by California; since then California has reduced the number of TB cases by 60% (CDPH, 2014). Out of 2,169 new TB cases reported in 2013, 78% were among foreign born persons and 6% were among homeless persons (CDPH, 2014).

Many other countries have higher rates of TB compared to the U.S. and use Bacillus Calmette-Guerrin (BCG) vaccine as a method to attempt to prevent TB disease (CDC, 2014). For 2013, the Center for Immigration Studies reported California as the top ranking state with the largest number of immigrants in their population (Camarota and Zeigler, 2014). Serving a large foreign born population requires the use of

appropriate screening tools to ensure this population is screened for LTBI with a method that is not affected by prior vaccination with BCG and provides accurate results. The target county in 2013 reported 666 new TB cases of which 79.4% were foreign born.

The second population affecting TB rates in California is the homeless. Despite declining trends in new TB cases among the homeless since 1994, the numbers of new cases has been slowly increasing starting in 2009 (Figure 1; CDPH, 2015). Furthermore, in 2013, the target county reported 666 new TB cases (incidence rate 7.1 per 100,000) of which 9.8% (65 cases) were among the homeless; depicting an increase of 3.5% from 2012 (CDPH, 2014).

Figure 1. Homeless TB cases in California, 2009-2013 (CDPH, 2015).

Screening Tests for Tuberculosis

The TST was developed in 1907 and has since been the primary test for LTBI screening (Iqbal et al., 2013). Furthermore, “the TST is based on delayed-type hypersensitivity immune response 48-72 h after 0.1 ml of purified TB protein derivative is intradermally introduced into the forearm” (Iqbal et al., 2013, p.144). At the time of reading the TST, providers must measure and interpret the results of the immune response allowing for variability. Although it has been in use for a long period of time, the TST is not without limitations. One limitation is high false-positive results due to prior BCG vaccination (Iqbal et al., 2013). Although BCG is not used in the U.S. due to insufficient evidence to suggest that it is effective in preventing tuberculosis, it is widely used in foreign countries. Other limitations of the TST include interpreter bias and the need for two visits to obtain results (Iqbal et al., 2013; Schluger & Burzynski, 2010). Compliance due to poor patient follow up skin test readings is especially problematic among high risk populations including the homeless (CDC, 1992). In addition, for those persons with a positive TST, a chest x-ray (CXR) is required to complete the screening process, which may require another visit as well as additional cost for the test.

In 2001, a new blood test was developed to test for LTBI called Interferon Gamma Release Assay (IGRA). IGRA is a blood test used in LTBI screening which requires the drawing of blood with subsequent laboratory processing.

IGRAs measure a person’s immune reactivity to *M. tuberculosis*. White blood cells from most persons that have been infected with *M. tuberculosis* will release interferon-gamma (IFN-g) when mixed with antigens (substances that can produce an immune response) derived from *M. tuberculosis*. (CDC, 2011, p. 1)

There are currently two approved CDC IGRAs for LTBI testing: (a) Quantiferon- TB Gold in Tube test (QFT-GIT) and (b) SPOT TB test (TSPOT). For those who have received BCG and probable non-compliant persons with TST screening, IGRAs have been identified by CDC as the recommended screening tool (CDC, 2011). Benefits of using an IGRA include the single patient visit and reduced false-positive results for those previously vaccinated with the BCG vaccine.

In 2012, the target county reported using IGRA at time of diagnosis in only 21.1% of cases however in 2013 they reported an increase to 45.5% (CDPH, 2014). Documented barriers related to the use of IGRA include provider lack of knowledge of the test, lack of experience with the test, and a general unease over cost (Joseph et al., 2004). Anecdotally, staff members are conscious of the need to be cost efficient in the organization but express unease of using the test due to a lack of blood drawing competency. Studies have shown the cost of an IGRA test ranges from \$25 to \$50 depending on the brand in comparison to a TST with a cost of approximately \$11 (Joseph et al., 2004). Besides cost, there are additional barriers in using IGRA in the field by public health nursing staff. Some barriers include the number of blood tubes required, the need for incubation or delivery to the lab, and lack of phlebotomy experience.

Supporting Framework

The framework chosen for this project is the Logic Model (Figure 2). The Logic Model as described by Taylor-Powell, Jones, and Henert (2003) contains three main components that are interrelated and shows the sequence of events that bring about change; these three main components are (a) resources that are invested, (b) the activities that take place and (c) the benefits or changes that result.

- Input- what is invested
- Output- what is done
- Outcomes/Impact- what the results are

In this project, inputs are the following: staff, patients, cost, laboratory, and guidelines/recommendations from the county's Tuberculosis Control Program (TBCP) and the CDC. Staff invests time in learning and implementing the new test and patients invest time in getting screened for LTBI. In both cases, potential usefulness of the screening test and barriers to implementation affect individual perspectives. Cost is an administrative input as the administration has to justify what is being spent. The laboratory -- both internal and external -- invests time in training staff, as well as providing guidance with use and purchasing of the product. The CDC and TBCP provide the necessary guidelines to ensure effective implementation of IGRAs within clinical practice.

Outputs for this project are divided into two categories. The first is activities, which include those things that are done; the second is participation, which involves the target population for those activities (Taylor-Powell et al., 2003). For this project, the first category includes the following:

- Implement a policy for the use of IGRA in field testing
- Training for staff on IGRA and TB cluster information
- Develop relationships with laboratories to use IGRA
- Pilot test IGRA with public health nursing field staff

These activities all lead to staff and target population participation, which results in clinician awareness of the benefits of the use of IGRA and increased patient compliance in screening.

The last component of the logic model details the outcomes and impact. These are further sub-categorized into short, medium, and long-term outcomes (Taylor-Powell et al., 2003). The short-term outcomes for this project are measures that will allow the evaluation of successful implementation of IGRA in the public health nursing field setting: (a) usage of IGRA in the field, (b) completion of screening rates, and (c) costs. The medium-term outcome is an improvement of LTBI screening with an IGRA-based test for targeted populations that should ultimately lead to the long term outcome of reducing the rates of TB disease.

Figure 2. Evaluation for IGRA implementation in Field Public Health Nursing Logic Model

Purpose Statement

The purpose of this project is to provide an evaluation of the use of LTBI tests in contact investigations in the field setting in a large urban county health system in California. This evaluation is composed of three parts. The first component will measure usage of IGRA in the field following implementation that includes a policy change and documented staff training in May of 2014. The second component will document a comparison of TBCP data from January through June 2013 to January through June 2014 on completion screening rates for contacts of tuberculosis cases. The last component is a cost analysis of TST vs. IGRA in the field setting including cost of test, staff time, and cost of CXR as well as a cost impact analysis for LTBI treatment. Implementation of IGRA use is expected to improve screening, reduce the use of x-ray and x-ray exposure to patients as well as reduce unnecessary LTBI treatment. Ultimately, it is expected to reduce cost for a large local health department with a high incidence of TB.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

A literature review was performed using computerized databases on the following topics to help support this project: (a) IGRA as a screening test for LTBI, (b) LTBI screening for contacts and target populations and (c) cost analysis for the use of IGRA. Several databases were used to look at peer reviewed articles written in English on all three topics within the last ten years. The results for each section are discussed below.

IGRA as a Screening Test for LTBI

Since 2001 when IGRA tests were developed for TB, many studies have explored the use of IGRA as a replacement for the TST (Diel et al., 2011; Menzies, Madhukar & Comstock, 2007; Sadatsafavi et al., 2010; Schluger & Burzynski, 2010). In order to ensure that an IGRA could replace the TST, researchers had to show that IGRA results were the same if not better in sensitivity and specificity for testing for LTBI compared to a TST. As Diel et al. explain, “for a new test to replace the TST, evidence of the tests’ higher diagnostic accuracy is needed” (2011, p. 89). Sensitivity is defined as the “tests’ ability to yield a positive result when the person actually has the condition, disorder or disease” (Macha & McDonough, 2012, p. 176) and specificity is the “tests’ ability to yield a negative result when the person does not have the condition, disorder, or disease” (p. 176).

Three meta-analyses (Diel et al., 2011; Menzies, Madhukar & Comstock, 2007; Sadatsafavi et al., 2010) and one literature review (Schluger & Burzynski, 2010) have been conducted to explore sensitivity and specificity to show that IGRA test are evidence based. As discussed earlier, the two CDC-approved IGRA tests are QFT and TSPOT. Two meta-analyses used the sensitivity and specificity for QFT, TSPOT and TST as

variables in their study; while Diel et al. (2011) used specificity of the tests, negative predictive value (NPV) and positive predictive value (PPV) for progression to TB disease as variables for their study.

While sensitivity results for all three tests were similar by study (Table 1), there were some differences in the TSPOT and QFT findings of Sadatsafavi et al. (2010). Sadatsafavi et al. (2010) reported a sensitivity of 50% for TSPOT, much lower than those reported by the others. As the authors explain in the limitations, this meta-analysis had only 19 studies of which only three met the inclusion criteria for the TSPOT test (Sadatsavi et al., 2010). As a result the authors explain that “the parameter estimates for TSPOT is probably unreliable” (Sadatsavi et al., 2010, p. 264). Results for QFT were consistent at 76% with Schluger and Burzynski (2010) and Menzies et al. (2007); slightly lower was the 64.2% reported by Sadatsafavi et al. TST results were consistent at 71% among Schluger and Burzynski (2010) and Sadatsafavi et al. (2010) but were slightly lower for the results presented by Menzies et al. (2007) at 63%.

Table 1

Sensitivity for LTBI Test as Reported in Studies

Authors	Sensitivity		
	QFT	TSPOT	TST
Schluger & Burzynski (2010)	76%	88-90%	71%
Menzies, Madhukar & Comstock (2007)	76%	88%	63%
Sadatsafavi et al. (2010)	64%	50%	71%

Results for specificity for all three tests were also similar and showed that IGRA tests have a very high specificity compared to the TST (Table 2). Although the results from Diel et al. (2011) were higher for TST at 88.7% (range of 55-95%) compared to

66% reported by Schluger and Burzynski (2010) and Menzies et al. (2007), IGRAs still had a higher specificity than TST. As explained by Diel et al., “these results suggest that the IGRAs are more certain to correctly identify individuals not infected with *M. Tuberculosis* as compared to the TST” (2011, p. 94). Furthermore, Diel et al. (2007) explain that IGRA test measure antigens specific to *M. Tuberculosis* and therefore “unlike the TST, the newest commercial IGRAs are not affected by prior BCG vaccination” (p. 95).

Table 2

Specificity for LTBI Test as Reported in Studies

Authors	Specificity		
	QFT	TSPOT	TST
Schluger & Burzynski (2010)	97%	88-92%	66%
Menzies, Madhukar & Comstock (2007)	97.7%	92.5%	66%
Sadatsafavi et al. (2010)	99.6%	90.6%	68.3%
Diel et al. (2011)	100%	98%	88.7% (range 55-95%)

LTBI Screening for Contacts and Target Populations

Screening contacts and target populations is fundamental to tuberculosis control and a main function of local health departments. For almost a century, the TST has been the main method of testing for LTBI; however recent advances in technology have resulted in the development of new tests for LTBI (Nienhaus, Schablon, Costa, & Diel, 2011). These tests are called IGRA and can offer more benefits in certain populations compared to a TST (Nienhaus et al., 2011).

Foreign born individuals make up 78% of all TB cases in California (CDPH, 2014). Screening and treatment of LTBI in this population is critical to the reduction of TB disease and IGRA tests are an important factor in ensuring appropriate testing. Completion of screening is defined as (a) a negative TST or IGRA or (b) a positive TST or IGRA with a negative CXR.

As discussed earlier, IGRA test have a very high specificity rate compared to TST because IGRA test-specific *M. Tuberculosis* antigens are not affected by prior BCG vaccination or *Nontuberculous Mycobacterium* (CDC, 2014; Diel et al., 2011; Menzies, Madhukar & Comstock, 2007; Sadatsafavi et al, 2010; Schluger & Burzynski, 2010). Menzies et al. (2007) report that rates of false positive results on TST can be as high as 40% post vaccination; Sadatsafavi et al. (2010) report similar findings of 50% in all persons. Schluger and Bruzynski (2010) stated it best when they said “there is no question that IGRAs are superior in testing for latent infection in foreign-born people with a history of prior BCG vaccination” (p. 1459).

The incidence of TB can be up to 20 times higher in the homeless (Tankimovich, 2013; Yun et al., 2003). In addition, TB outbreaks in the homeless continue to be an issue that challenges TB control efforts (Dobbins et al., 2012; Nyamathi et al., 2008; Yun et al., 2003). Numerous difficulties exist in screening the homeless population (Dobbins et al., 2012; Nyamathi et al., 2008; Tankimovich, 2013; Yun et al., 2003). Cultural, socio-political, and socioeconomic difficulties exist for both immigrants as well as the homeless (Tankimovich, 2013, p. 84). Both groups present a number of barriers in the screening of LTBI due to factors such as fear due to legal status, lack of trust in government, greater exposure to high risk factors, and housing instability (Tankimovich,

2013). In addition, the use of illegal substances is a major barrier in screening for LTBI (Dobbins et al., 2012; Nyamathi et al., 2008; Tankimovich, 2013; Yun et al., 2003).

Following a literature review of barriers related to these populations as well as effective interventions appropriate for immigrants and the homeless in screening for LTBI, Tankimovich (2013) concludes that in addition to affordable, accessible care and providing monetary incentives, a critical component of a successful intervention is to use new technology and improved methods for screening.

There are a number of limitations related to the TST, including returning for a second visit, interpreter bias, and false positive results due to BCG (CDC, 2014; Diel et al., 2011; Iqbal et al., 2013; Menzies, Madhukar & Comstock, 2007; Sadatsafavi et al., 2010; Schluger & Burzynski, 2010; Trieu, Proops & Ahuja, 2013). These limitations are not present when using an IGRA; patients do not have to return for a second visit and interpreter bias and false positive results are removed as a result of the test. However, other limitations exist when using an IGRA primarily the need for phlebotomy and higher cost (CDC, 2014; Diel et al., 2011; Menzies, Madhukar & Comstock, 2007; Sadatsafavi et al., 2010; Schluger & Burzynski, 2010; Trieu et al., 2013). Most authors support Schluger and Bruzynski (2010) in suggesting that the advantages from using an IGRA outweigh the limitations:

These tests offer major operational and biological advantages over the TST, and on a large scale, because of their greatly increased accuracy, their use could be cost saving and should dramatically reduce the number of patients treated inappropriately for latent TB infection. (p. 1462)

As a result of the compelling evidence, the CDC (2014) recommends the use of IGRA specifically for “persons who have received BCG (either as a vaccine or for cancer therapy); and persons from groups that historically have poor rates of return for TST reading” (para. 6).

In addition to aligning the large local health department with CDC guidelines, the policy implementation also includes the use of IGRA in the field for contact investigations. Given the recency of IGRA introduction, few field trials of its use have been published and there is limited data on the topic (Trieu, Proops, & Ahuja, 2013). In a small sample of 42 contacts, Trieu et al. screened 95% of those using QFT; they posit that their completion rates might have been lower with a TST. Dewan et al. (2006), in a large sample of 4,143 immigrants, homeless, and intravenous drug users, showed that when using IGRA, 92% of results were available and 74% of those with a positive IGRA result completed screening.

In the past, contact investigations in the field have primarily been performed with a TST and completion rates for screening have varied due to the limitations of TST. A study of contact investigations in California with 17,774 contacts evaluated by TST revealed an 87.7% completion rate falling short of the CDC target of 95% (Sprinson et al., 2003). A second study looking at contact investigations using TST in five areas across the United States ($n = 3,824$) revealed a 55% completion rate (Reichler et al., 2002). Both studies provided aggregate reports for all contacts and did not report findings for special target populations.

Dewan et al. (2006) compared their results of 92% result availability to several other studies with similar populations using TST for testing and claimed favorable outcomes:

in similar patient populations in other cities, 84% at a needle exchange program in Baltimore, 64% at a public health program in Atlanta, and 47% in a street outreach program for drug users in Long Beach. (p. 53)

A third study evaluating contact investigations among the homeless found similar findings with a 52% completion rate (Yun et al., 2003). In addition, Dewan et al. (2006) report a patient refusal rate due to phlebotomy at only 8%. Although there are very limited studies in this area, the current evidence supports the benefits of using IGRA in the field and possibilities of increased screening completion rates. However, further evidence is needed to show that IGRA can improve screening completion rates in contact investigations.

Cost Analysis for IGRA

Since the development of IGRA test in 2001, adoption of this new technology has been slow across the country (Joseph et al., 2004). One of the main barriers is concern of increased cost compared to TST. As reported earlier the upfront cost of an IGRA test ranges from \$25 to \$50 depending on the brand in comparison to a TST with a cost of approximately \$11 (Joseph et al., 2004). Several studies document the cost effectiveness and cost benefit of IGRA compared to TST (Dewan et al., 2006; Iqbal et al., 2013; Kowada, 2013; Miller et al., 2006; Nienhaus et al., 2011).

Nienhaus et al. (2011), who conducted a systematic review on the topic, states that “cost-effectiveness studies are done as part of a complete economic evaluation with

the aim of comparing the costs and consequences of various measures” (p. 251). These studies look at quality adjusted life years, life years gained, and incremental cost effectiveness ratios as the most common measures for determining cost effectiveness. However, studies can have different methods and measure multiple different factors such as negative and positive predictive value, length of time period studied, percentages of sensitivity and specificity, as well as many other different variables (Dewan et al., 2006; Iqbal et al., 2013; Kowada, 2013; Miller et al., 2006; Nienhaus et al., 2011).

The percentages used for the specificity and sensitivity can impact the results of the cost effectiveness study (Nienhaus et al., 2011). In the studies reviewed by Nienhaus et al. (2011), the assumed specificity and sensitivity for TST and IGRA depended on the study and the country. For TST, the specificity varied from 15% to 98% and for IGRA from 95 to 100% with the studies from Japan assuming the lowest percentages. Similarly the sensitivity for TST ranged from 67% to 99% and 76% to 100% for IGRA. Variability of the assumed specificity and sensitivity was also true for the other cost effectiveness studies (Iqbal et al., 2013; Kowada, 2013).

In addition, variables used to measure cost for IGRA and TST varied extensively by study, but were reasonable as there is no standardized definition for measuring cost and each health department has different cost analysis processes. Components that were often measured included cost of screening test, cost of staff time to perform the test, cost of CXR, cost of radiology time, and cost for LTBI treatment including medications and clinic visits (Dewan et al., 2006; Iqbal et al., 2013; Kowada, 2013; Miller et al., 2006; Nienhaus et al., 2011). Looking specifically at the cost of test, one component of this can be the staff time necessary to perform the procedure. Iqbal et al. (2013), Kowada (2013),

and Dewan et al. (2006) all measured professional cost based on actual staff wages while Miller et al. (2006) used the “midpoint of Medicare’s national average allowance and mean fee for non-Medicare charges” (p. 307). Nienhaus et al. (2011) report that among the 13 studies they evaluated, costs of the TST and IGRA could not be compared because some studies used the manufacturer’s costs needed to perform the tests and other studies also took the cost of manpower into consideration or combined costs for testing with costs for CXRs, chemoprevention and costs for hepatitis developed during INH treatment. (p. 256)

Regardless of these limitations, all studies, with the exception of Iqbal et al. (2013), found that IGRA had decreased costs for LTBI screening compared to using a TST primarily due to the high specificity of IGRA and the lack of interaction with prior BCG vaccine (Dewan et al., 2006; Kowada, 2013; Miller et al., 2006; Nienhaus et al., 2011). Iqbal et al. (2013) reported that this was true for foreign born populations but found that U.S. born populations had lower cost with TST. Limitations of their study were the small sample of only 221 patients and that the study was conducted in an area with low TB prevalence (Iqbal et al., 2013). All authors agreed with Iqbal et al. (2011) that biggest cost burden for a health departments is not the screening test but the other costs such as follow up diagnostic work up, the lengthy treatment regiment, and follow up tests at clinic visits.

In general, cost effectiveness studies have shown that IGRA is a more cost effective test for LTBI screening. However, due to the variability of measures across all of the studies, it is very difficult to compare costs for TST and IGRA. “Comparison of these studies is hampered not only by the different cost assumed and different

assumptions on test parameters used in the studies but also by different strategies in modeling and different outcomes used” (Nienhaus et al., 2011, p. 256).

METHODS

This project took place in a large local health department in the state of California with a high incidence of TB cases. Data abstracted from TBCP included laboratory results for tests performed by approximately 180 field public health nurses. A policy and procedure outlining the use of IGRAs in the field was implemented within the department in April 2014. Following policy implementation, a training of IGRA procedures was provided to public health nursing staff by the vendor. Lastly, training was provided to all public health nurses by the administration at the beginning of May 2014 to present the rationale for the change in practice and to review questions and concerns regarding implementation of the policy and procedure. An IRB application was filed with the local health department and a letter of exemption was received on October 8, 2014 as this project utilizes data which is routinely collected as part of the surveillance process for the local health department. An IRB application was filed with the school and approved on October 29, 2014 .

IGRA Usage

Data was abstracted from monthly reports provided by the laboratory which provide the number of IGRA tests performed in the field by public health nurses at 12 separate sites. Data was trended monthly per site to determine differences in usage of the new test for TB testing in the field. Data was obtained from January 2014 to December 2014 with a special note on usage after May 2014 post training and implementation of an IGRA policy for field usage.

Screening Completion and LTBI Rates

Data was abstracted from the local health department to evaluate screening completion rates and LTBI rates for all contacts screened. For the purposes of this project, screening completion rates is defined as a complete diagnostic evaluation for LTBI which means that if a patient is IGRA negative no further testing is needed and if a patient is IGRA positive then a CXR is done to rule out TB disease. A comparison was made using data from January through June 2013 compared to data from January through June 2014. These time frames were chosen in order to compare the same time period for both years. Data for 2012 was also included to provide a baseline for LTBI rate prior to any usage of IGRA for this local health department.

Data was abstracted from the local health department's TBCP aggregated reports for tuberculosis program evaluation (ARPE), provided to the California Department of Public Health (CDPH) on a biannual basis. A Chi Square test between proportions was performed with SPSS software to determine if there was a significant difference between the LTBI rates for the two time periods and LTBI rates were compared to the CDC estimated rate for LTBI.

Cost-Analysis

A Microsoft Excel spreadsheet was used to perform the cost analysis for screening and treatment between TST and IGRA as well as to calculate the cost impact analysis for LTBI treatment. Patients are provided treatment at net county cost regardless of insurance coverage. For the cost analysis: tests, prescriptions and CXR were calculated using the health department's cost and staff time was calculated using the health department's estimated weighted annual salary.

The LTBI screening category includes the cost of the test, number of visits, and public health nursing time (15 minutes) to administer the test. The category of LTBI treatment includes three components: CXR cost, prescription cost and clinic visit cost. The CXR cost includes the cost of the CXR, 10 min of the radiologist technician's time and 15 min of the radiologist physician (MD) time. The cost of the prescriptions included nine months of treatment with daily Isoniazid (INH) and Vitamin B6. Staff time for the clinic visits include: a one-time visit with a physician, nine visits with a Registered Nurse (RN), nine visits with the clerk and 10 min blood draw time with an RN for nine visits. It also includes a one-time baseline liver function test that includes Alanine Amino Transferase (ALT), Aspartate Amino Transferase (AST), Total Bilirubin, Creatinine, Blood Urea Nitrogen and a Complete Blood Count with Differential; along with nine months of follow up test to monitor the liver using AST and ALT only. The cost analysis did not include administrative overhead for any of its services which include fees related to the facility and salaries for administrative staff and oversight.

Lastly, a cost impact analysis for LTBI treatment was done via excel spread sheet, comparing the LTBI rate for January through June 2012 when only TST was used with January through June 2014 and using the total cost of the LTBI treatment.

RESULTS

Data was collected from 12 sites that perform TB screening in the field setting. One site was removed due to the inability to separate field tests from tests done in the clinic. For 2014 there were a total of 550 TB cases investigated by public health nurses.

IGRA Usage

Results for the usage of IGRA overall were very successful and showed a steady incline trend from month to month. Usage of IGRA increased by more than 800% from 68 tests performed in January to 589 tests performed in December of 2014 (Figure 3). The number of TB cases reported per month showed a steady distribution by month with a slight increase in December.

Figure 3. 2014 IGRA usage in the field.

Comparison across sites showed varied results and revealed that some sites adopted the use of IGRA in the field much easier than others. There were five sites (sites A, B, C, D and E) that showed very low usage of IGRA tests throughout the year (Figure 4). The remaining sites all used over 100 IGRA tests over the course of one year with site F using 1,086 IGRA tests in the field throughout the year.

The remaining six sites (sites F, G, H, I, J and K) showed the majority of the usage of IGRA tests throughout the year with site F having the highest yield at 1,086 tests and site J leading second with 630 tests throughout the year.

Figure 4. 2014 IGRA usage by site.

For the sites that had lower than 100 tests performed over one year, monthly trending is pictured in Figure 5. The highest number of tests performed was site C with 55 IGRA tests over the period of one year. The monthly tracking of data showed that site C began usage of IGRA in the field in November and continued in December; while sites A, D and E began usage in the month of December. Site B remained without usage throughout the year with a total of zero IGRA test used in the field.

Figure 5. 2014 IGRA Usage by Sites with Less than 100 Tests.

Screening Completion and LTBI Rates

Data for screening completion and LTBI rates was collected from the TBCP from biannual ARPE reports for the months of January through June for both 2013 and 2014. Screening completion rates is defined as a complete diagnostic evaluation for LTBI which means that if a patient is IGRA negative no further testing is needed and if a patient is IGRA positive then a CXR is done to rule out TB disease. Screening completion rates as detailed in table 3 showed that the completion rates were similar for 2013 and 2014 with very minimal variation. There was a large decrease of 1,840 contacts noted from year 2013 to year 2014 and a difference of 35 TB cases.

Table 3

ARPE Report Screening Completion

	Number of TB Cases Investigated	Number of Contacts	Number of Contacts Screened	Percent completed Screening
Jan to June 2013	178	3223	3146	97.6%
Jan to June 2014	143	1383	1337	96.6%

Figure 6 shows the percentages for the LTBI rate for January through June 2012 (used as a baseline), January through June 2013 and January through June 2014. A Chi Square test was performed for the periods of 2013 and 2014 and showed that there was a significant difference $X^2(1, N = 3731) = 31.85, p < .0001$, between LTBI rates for January through June 2013 and January through June 2014. Furthermore, the results showed that the 2014 data was closer to the CDC estimated LTBI rate of 5-10% for general populations (CDC, 2012).

Figure 6. 2013 and 2014 Latent TB Infection Rates Comparison.

Cost Analysis

The cost analysis was completed using an excel spreadsheet to calculate the cost for screening and treatment as well as a cost impact analysis for LTBI. Results showed that despite a higher cost of screening with IGRA (table 4), in the long run, the use of IGRA has more cost savings than a TST as there are more accurate screening results. IGRA has a higher specificity than a TST and therefore there are less false positives resulting in a reduction of total number of persons who need treatment for LTBI. This results in a decreased number of CXR and LTBI treatment (including prescriptions and clinic visits) and lower overall cost to the organization.

Table 4

Cost for LTBI Screening with TST and IGRA

ITEM	TST	IGRA
Test	0.28	46.50
PHN Time 15 min visit 1	13.28	13.28
PHN Time 15 min visit 2	13.28	0.00
Screening Total	\$26.84	\$59.78

The cost of the LTBI treatment detailed in table 5, remains the same regardless of what test is used for screening, therefore only one cost for treatment was calculated which resulted in a total of \$270.88 for a nine month course of treatment. The total amount is a cumulative amount including all CXR, prescriptions and clinic visits for nine months of treatment necessary to complete the regimen. The components in the cost of the LTBI treatment included: results for the CXR at \$69.17 for only one view taken; \$21.60 for prescription medications; and \$180.11 for clinic visits necessary for a nine month treatment. Total cost for TST screening and treatment resulted in \$297.72 and the total cost for IGRA screening and treatment resulted in \$330.66.

The cost impact analysis was calculated using an excel spread sheet using the latent TB infection rate for TST (data from 2012) and IGRA (data from 2014). Due to the specificity of IGRA, the latent TB infection rate was smaller and therefore it resulted in less LTBI positive persons. Using a TST the total positive was 217 and with IGRA the total positive was 131. The number of LTBI positives was multiplied by the cost of the 9 month treatment for LTBI. With a TST the total cost of treatment for all those who are positive would be \$64,605.24 compared those tested with an IGRA which resulted in a total of \$43,316.46 (Figure 6). The results show that there would be \$21,288.78 in cost

savings to the organization from using IGRA compared to a TST. This cost savings is a result of less false positives due to an increased specificity of the IGRA test and reduced LTBI false positives.

Table 5

Cost for LTBI Treatment

Xray 1 view	5.60
Radiology Technician 15 min	7.32
Radiologist MD 15 min	56.25
Xray Total	\$69.17
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INH 300mg x9 mos	18.90
B6 50mg x9 mos	2.70
Prescription Total	\$21.60
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Baseline Liver Function test x1	7.50
Follow up AST/ALT x9	2.20
RN blood draw 10 min	8.10
MD visit 15 min x1	24.41
RN visit 15 min x9	109.37
Clerk 10 min x9	28.53
Clinic Visit x9 mos Total	\$180.11
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9 MONTHS LTBI TREATMENT TOTAL	\$270.88

Figure 7. Cost Impact Analysis Results.

DISCUSSION

Evidence based practice (EBP) is an essential component of improving nursing practice and improving patient outcomes. Wallis (2012) explains that EBP “leads to better, safer care; better outcomes and lower health care costs” (p. 15). However, despite the benefits of EBP, Wallis also expresses that “nurses in the United States aren’t consistently using it” (p. 15). Berwick (2003) further explains that “failing to use available science is costly and harmful; it leads to overuse of unhelpful care, underuse of effective care, and errors in execution” (p. 1969). Regardless of all the known advantages of implementing evidence based practices by nurses, Wuchner (2014) explains that there is very little evidence detailing effective strategies to do so. As seen in this project the implementation of evidence based practice supported by a change in policy and staff training, does not necessarily translate to adoption by nurses.

IGRA Usage

Despite the fact that IGRA usage was an overall success this evaluation detailed the lack of implementation among certain sites. In addition, it also identified sites that were willing and ready to change their practice from the start. As Berwick (2003) discusses, it is important to identify these groups and provide support as necessary. Supporting staff that are ready and willing to adopt a new practice is just as important as supporting staff that are hesitant and not ready to change their practice. This continued support can encourage staff to adopt new practices once they see and hear that others have successfully done so. As we see in this project we had four sites that did not begin adoption of the test until very late in the year and one site that did not do any at all. One reason for this is that in September the data was brought to the attention of the nurse

managers at a meeting and the nurse managers reviewed those sites that had low usage. The nurse managers then began working with these specific sites and address barriers to adoption of the new practice and encouraged usage of IGRA in the field.

This project is a good example of why nursing leaders must take careful measures to ensure that an evaluation component is part of any implementation of evidence based practice. In addition, it is not sufficient to look at overall data but the evaluation must also be detailed enough to possibly identify barriers at an individual level.

Limitations of this component include not being able to have the total number of contacts that needed to be screened per month. Having this information would have provided the author with the ability to calculate a true rate of adoption by the PHNs. In addition, this evaluation did not perform a formal evaluation to identify the reasons why staff did not adopt the practice.

Screening Completion and LTBI Rates

In 2013 minimal use of IGRA was existent within the department and only available in the clinic setting whereas in 2014 implementation of IGRA was implemented both in the field and the clinic. However, we cannot conclude that this change was due to the use of IGRA alone based on the data provided. This is because it is not possible to identify which contacts received a TST and which ones received an IGRA test. Having the ability to identify and separate these categories would have been beneficial in identifying if there were really true changes based on the test used. Furthermore, in December 2012 this local health department was impacted by a TB outbreak among the homeless. As discussed earlier, the homeless have higher rates of latent TB infection which may have affected the results for 2013. Further tracking needs to be done in order

to ensure a continued decrease of latent TB infection rates along with increased usage of IGRA for TB screening. In addition to the limitation listed above, there were other limitations of this component. Screening completion rates showed very minimal changes between both time periods; however this data does not capture the number of attempts made by the PHNs to ensure screenings are completed. Despite the fact that screening completion rates are fairly high, it does not provide information on the resources necessary to accomplish that task. These resources include, the PHN time to locate patients which may take multiple attempts either by phone and/or in person out in the field. It is also important to mention that the PHNs primary responsibility is to ensure completion of the contact screening to prevent disease and they go above and beyond to ensure their work is complete.

In addition, note should be made to the variance in the number of contacts for the time periods evaluated. Although 2014 reflected a decrease of 35 TB cases investigated, this decrease did not match up to the large decrease of contacts identified. In 2013 there were a total of 3,223 contacts identified compared to 1383 in 2014 with a difference of 1,840 contacts. Reasons for this variance are unknown, however there were a couple of factors that may have caused this which include (a) a TB homeless outbreak identified in December 2012 which resulted in more cases and screening of contact during the 2013 year and (b) a decrease of cases in 2014 due to a continued decline of TB and effective efforts in preventing the transmission of disease among the homeless population.

Cost Analysis

The findings for the cost-analysis are consistent with other studies performed as discussed in the literature review. IGRA tests are more costly and the cost of screening is still more expensive with IGRA than a TST despite the fact that only one visit is needed for IGRA. The cost impact analysis for LTBI showed that even though screening with IGRA is more expensive, in the long run using IGRA reduces the number of false positives and will therefore reduce the number of patients requiring CXR and LTBI treatment. As a result, with a predictive model using 1,000 patients the local health department would save \$21,288.78 for every 1,000 patients screened for LTBI. In addition, there are additional opportunity costs that are not detailed in the cost analysis. Opportunity costs relates to the amount of time and possible loss of wages that would be incurred by the patient for having to attend monthly clinic visits for nine months or the duration of the treatment. These costs can vary per patient and can be numerous considering the length of the treatment.

Limitations for this component include the lack of information regarding the return rate for the second visit with TST. The literature shows that especially with high risk individuals the return rate for a TST reading is very poor. Since IGRA only requires one initial visit, this greatly increases the screening completion rate with only one visit. Furthermore, the predictive analysis relies on latent TB infection rates, which as discussed earlier, is not exclusive to only those tested with IGRA.

Recommendations

In conclusion, the use of IGRA in the field is a cost effective evidence based practice that should be implemented across all local health departments. Implementation

of any evidence based practice with the nursing workforce benefits not only the staff but most importantly patient outcomes and satisfaction. It is important with implementation to ensure an evaluation component that provides detailed information so that staff can be supported and encouraged through the adoption process. Further studies are recommended to identify effective strategies for implementing evidence based practices within the nursing workforce. Studies are also needed to elicit staff opinions about the barriers to implementation of an evidence based practice to better identify strategies to overcome these barriers.

REFERENCES

- Berwick, D. (2003). Disseminating innovations in health care. *Journal of the American Medical Association*, 289(15), 1969-1975.
- Boston University of Public Health (2013). *Diffusion of innovation theory*. Retrieved from <http://sphweb.bumc.bu.edu/otlt/MPH-Modules/SB/SB721-Models/SB721-Models4.html>
- California Department of Public Health. (2014). *Report on tuberculosis in California, 2013*. Retrieved from http://www.cdph.ca.gov/programs/tb/Documents/TBCB_Report_2013.pdf
- California Department of Public Health. (2015). *Tuberculosis disease data*. Retrieved from <http://www.cdph.ca.gov/data/statistics/Pages/TuberculosisDiseaseData.aspx>
- Camarota, S. A. & Zeigler, K. (2014). U.S. Immigrant Population Record 41.3 Million in 2013. *Center for Immigration Studies*. Retrieved from <http://cis.org/immigrant-population-record-2013>
- Centers for Disease Control. (1991). Prevention and control of tuberculosis in U.S. communities with at-risk minority populations: Recommendations of the advisory council for the elimination of tuberculosis and prevention and control of tuberculosis among homeless persons. *Mortality and Morbidity Weekly Report*, 41(RR-5), 1-5.
- Centers for Disease Control. (2011). *TB elimination: Interferon Gamma Release Assay (IGRAs) - Blood test for TB infection*. Retrieved from <http://www.cdc.gov/tb/publications/factsheets/testing/IGRA.pdf>

- Centers for Disease Control (2012). *Self study modules on tuberculosis*. Retrieved from <http://www.cdc.gov/tb/education/ssmodules/module6/ss6decision.htm>
- Centers for Disease Control (2014). *Tuberculosis*. Retrieved from <http://www.cdc.gov/tb/>
- Dewan, P. K., Grinsdale, J., Liska, S., Wong, E., Fallstad, R., & Kawamura, L. M. (2006). Feasibility, acceptability, and cost of tuberculosis testing by whole-blood interferon-gamma assay. *BMC Infectious Diseases*, 6(1), 47-55.
- Diel, R., Goletti, D., Ferrara, G., Bothamley, G., Cirillo, D., Kampmann, B., . . . Manissero, D. (2011). Interferon- γ release assays for the diagnosis of latent mycobacterium tuberculosis infection: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *The European Respiratory Journal*, 37(1), 88-99.
- Dobbins, C., Marishta, K., Kuehnert, P., Arbisi, M., Darnall, E., Conover, C., . . . Haddad, M. (2012). Tuberculosis outbreak associated with a homeless shelter - Kane County, Illinois, 2007-2011. *Morbidity & Mortality Weekly Report*, 61(11), 186-189.
- Iqbal, A.Z., Leighton, J., Anthony, J., Knaup, R.C., Peters, E.B., & Bailey, T.C. (2013). Cost effectiveness of using quantiferon gold (QFT-G) versus tuberculin skin test (TST) among U.S. and foreign born populations at a public health department clinic with a low prevalence of tuberculosis. *Public Health Nursing*, 31(2), 144-152.
- Joseph, H.A., Shrestha-Kuwahara, R., Lowry, D., Lambert, L.A., Panlilio, A.L., Raucher, B., Holcombe, J.M., . . . Wilce, M. (2004). Factors influencing health care

- workers' adherence to work site tuberculosis screening and treatment policies. *American Journal of Infection Control*, 32(8), 456-461.
- Kowada, A. (2013). Cost-effectiveness of interferon-gamma release assay for entry tuberculosis screening in prisons. *Epidemiology & Infections*, 141(10), 2224-2234.
- Macha, K., & McDonough, J. P. (2012). *Epidemiology for advanced practice nursing*. Sudbury, MA: Jones & Bartlett.
- Menzies, D., Pai, M., & Comstock, G. (2007). Meta-analysis: New tests for the diagnosis of latent tuberculosis infection: Areas of uncertainty and recommendations for research. *Annals of Internal Medicine*, 146(5), 340-354.
- Miller, T., Hilsenrath, P., Lykens, K., McNabb, S., Moonan, P., & Weis, S. E. (2006). Using cost and health impacts to prioritize the targeted testing of tuberculosis in the United States. *Annals of Epidemiology*, 16(4), 305-312.
- Miramontes, R., Pratt, R., Price, S. F., Navin, T. R., & Lo, T. Q. (2013). Trends in tuberculosis- United States, 2012. *Mortality and Morbidity Weekly Report*, 62, 201-205.
- Nienhaus, A., Schablon, A., Costa, J. T., & Diel, R. (2011). Systematic review of cost and cost-effectiveness of different TB-screening strategies. *BMC Health Services Research*, 11(1), 247-257.
- Reichler, M., Reves, R., Bur, S., Thompson, V., Mangura, B., Ford, J., . . . Onorato, I.M. (2002). Evaluation of investigations conducted to detect and prevent transmission of tuberculosis. *The Journal of the American Medical Association*, 287(8), 991-995.

- Sadatsafavi, M., Shahidi, N., Marra, F., FitzGerald, M. J., Elwood, K. R., Guo, N., & Marra, C. A. (2010). A statistical method was used for the meta-analysis of tests for latent tb in the absence of a gold standard, combining random-effect and latent-class methods to estimate test accuracy. *Journal of Clinical Epidemiology*, 63(3), 257-269.
- Schluger, N., & Burzynski, J. (2010). Recent advances in testing for latent TB. *CHEST*, 138(6), 1456-1463.
- Sprinson, J., Flood, J., Fan, C. S., Shaw, T. A., Pascopella, L., & Royce, S. E. (2003). Evaluation of tuberculosis contact investigations in California. *The International Journal of Tuberculosis and Lung Disease*, 7(12 Suppl 3), S363-S368.
- Tankimovich, M. (2013). Barriers to and interventions for improved tuberculosis detection and treatment among homeless and immigrants populations: A literature review. *Journal of Community Health Nursing*, 30, 83-95.
- Taylor-Powell, E., Jones, L., & Henert, E. (2003). *Enhancing program performance with logic models*. Retrieved from <http://www.uwex.edu/ces/lmcourse/>
- Trieu, L., Proops, D. C., & Ahuja, S. D. (2013). Using quantiferon tb gold in tube for field based tuberculosis contact investigation in congregate settings. *Journal of Public Health Management Practice*, 19(3), E11-E13.
- Wallis, L. (2012). Barriers to implementing evidence-based practice remain high for u.s. nurses. *American Journal of Nursing*, 112(12), 15.
- World Health Organization. (2013, October). *Tuberculosis. Fact sheet no. 104*. Retrieved from <http://www.who.int/mediacentre/factsheets/fs104/en/>

Wuchner, S. (2014). Integrative review of implementation strategies for translation of research-based evidence by nurses. *Clinical Nurse Specialist CNS*, 28(4), 214-223.

Yun, L. W. H., Reves, R. R., Reichler, M. R., Bur, S., Thompson, V., Mangura, J., & Ford, J. (2003). Outcomes of contact investigation among homeless persons with infectious tuberculosis. *The International Journal of Tuberculosis and Lung Disease*, 7(12 Suppl 3), S405-S411.

APPENDIX

TABLES OF EVIDENCE FOR PROPOSAL

Table 1. *Screening for Latent Tuberculosis Infection and Use of IGRA*

Purpose (source)	Design, Key Variables	Sample/ Setting	Measures	Findings	Author Conclusions, Limitations
New advances in testing for LTBI (Schluger & Burzynski, 2010)	Literature review of TST and IGRA in LTBI testing TSPOT QFT TST	United States studies that used TST and IGRA for LTBI testing LTBI present in 20% of U.S. population	Looked at articles comparing TST and TSPOT Sensitivity and specificity for TST, QFT & TSPOT Foreign born Contacts to TB case	Sensitivity TST-71%; QFT-76%; TSPOT 88-90% Specificity TST-66%; QFT-97%; TSPOT 88-92% BCG given to 80 to 100 million person per year IGRA gives meaningful results >96% of the time One study showed that contacts tested with both TST and IGRA- more + results with IGRA vs TST	TST Operational limitations: injection administered properly, pts return for reading, measurement done correctly TST biological limitations: BCG results in false positive IGRA limitations: phlebotomy, incubation, cost Benefits of IGRA are by far the reduction of false positive tests and sensitivity and specificity. No boosting effect
Meta-analysis for diagnosis of LTBI (Menzies, Madhukar & Comstock, 2007)	Meta- analysis For use of IGRA in LTBI testing TB infection, TB disease and TSPOT, QFT, IGRA	Searched Medline for studies published in English from 1966 to 2006 110 studies; 52 excluded- 58 total LTBI screening in	Compared sensitivity, specificity and reproducibility Cross sectional studies only found	Pooled sensitivity TST-63%; QFT-76%; TSPOT-88% Pooled Specificity TST-66%; QFT-97.7%; TSPOT-92.5%	IGRA show greater specificity than TST. TST and IGRA had same sensitivity when categorized in clinical gradient of exposure BCG has great impact on specificity Limitations: only cross sectional

Purpose (source)	Design, Key Variables	Sample/ Setting	Measures	Findings	Author Conclusions, Limitations
		healthy adults and children			studies found; published in 2007, IGRA just released
Meta-analysis for LTBI test accuracy (Sadatsafavi et al., 2010)	Meta-analysis of agreement studies for TSPOT, QFT and TST Random effect latent class model used to estimate performance characteristics of tests	Searched PubMed through 6/1/2008 118 studies identified; 66 reviewed; 19 studies were included	Accuracy of test Goodness of fit stats for TST, QFT, TSPOT Correlation coefficients	Sensitivity TST 70.9%, QFT- 64.2%, TSPOT- 50% Specificity TST 68.3%, QFT- 99.6%, TSPOT- 90.6%	Since no gold standard for LTBI, statistical models are useful to estimate accuracy IGRAs have high specificity but low sensitivity Limitations: only 19 studies; TSPOT only 3 met inclusion criteria
Systemic review and meta-analysis for LTBI DX (Diel et al., 2011)	Systematic review and meta-analysis to compare the accuracy of QFT, TSPOT and TST	Medline, Embase and Cochrane databases in 11/2009 432 results; 324 screened. 60 studies used	Specificity= # true neg divided by sum of true neg and false pos NPV= true neg results divided by sum of true and false neg results NPV for progression = proportion of neg IGRA results that do not progress to active TB PPV for progression = proportion of pos results that do progress to TB	Specificity TSPOT 98; QFT 100%; TST pooled specificity 88.7% (range 55-95%) NPV TSPOT- 94%; QFT- 88% NPV for progression QFT 99.8%; TSPOT- 97.8% PPV for progression TST 2.3-3.3%; QFT- 2.8-14.3%; TSPOT 3.3-10%	Advantage of IGRA over TST in detecting LTBI

Note. LTBI = latent tuberculosis infection; TST = tuberculin skin test; IGRA = interferon gamma release assay; U.S. = United States; TSPOT = IGRA test; QFT = quantiferon; BCG = Bacilli Calmette Guerin; TB = tuberculosis; NPV = neg predictive value; PPV = positive predictive value; neg = negative; pos = positive; pts = patient; vs = versus; DX = diagnosis.

Table 2. *Tuberculosis Screening for Contacts and Targeted Populations*

Purpose (source)	Design, Key Variables	Sample/ Setting	Measures	Findings	Author Conclusions, Limitations
Barriers and interventions for LTBI detection and TX in homeless and immigrants (Tankimovich, 2013)	Systematic review of literature in LTBI detection and treatment to identify barriers and effective interventions	Medline, CINAHL, WHOSIS & CDC Hard to reach populations: homeless and immigrants 22 studies out of 80 published between 1998 and 2012	1. Barriers 2. Effective interventions	Barriers: health literacy, access to care, affordable care, cultural perception of TB, fear of illegal status, housing instability, co-morbidities (HIV); lack of technology and new advances in health care; Effective interventions: monetary incentives, accessible and affordable health care, cultural knowledge and coordination of all 3 above	Must use bio-psychosocial models that include cultural values of population Best interventions include a combo of money incentives & improved access to care Education is key to having pts understand why it is important Pts willing to receive care if they feel it's important
Evaluation of Nurse intervention with LTBI TX completion in homeless (Nyamathi et al., 2008)	2 group randomized design: DV- Treatment completion IV- Behavioral determinants of nonadherence to TX Intervention group (279) received 8 education training modules over 6 months before INH dose provided by nurses Control group (241)	520 homeless adults in 12 homeless shelters in skid row of LA 1998-2003 DX w/LTBI; 18-55; spent previous night in 1 of 12 selected shelters M=42 y.o., 80% male, 81% black, 7% white, 9.4% Hispanic	Treatment completion: direct observation of 52 doses of INH by DOT nurse TB knowledge assessed by 13 item instrument (validated) Intention to comply with TX assessed with 5 point scale Demographic factors	Intervention group 20% or more in treatment completion compared to control group Logistic regression- intervention most effective for daily ETOH, women, fair to poor health Shelter residents in intervention group had 91% completion rate	Nsg interventions in LTBI directly observed therapy are effective in increasing completion rates Limitations: intervention provided only in English- might have impacted foreign born patients. No discussion of attrition Note: list the typical completion rate for LTBI treatment or use the CDC target for LTBI treatment completion as a comparison

Purpose (source)	Design, Key Variables	Sample/ Setting	Measures	Findings	Author Conclusions, Limitations
	received one 20 min education session and tracking of INH was not done.	<i>M</i> = 1 year homeless			
Understand transmission of TB amongst homeless in shelter setting in Illinois (Dobbins et al., 2012)	Case control study Case group: men, part of an outbreak, slept at shelter at least 1 night in Aug 2006 Control group: men, slept at shelter at least 1 night in Aug 2006, neg for TB/ LTBI, no SX. DV: Transmission of TB IV: Self report characteristics and behaviors	TB outbreak in homeless shelter in Illinois 2007-2011 Case group: 17 out of 25 Control group: 23 out of 72 (only 24 found) 89% US born 50% black 50% white 14% Hispanic 82% homeless >1yr	Age, LOS at shelter, work history, smoked >1yr, use of excess ETOH, locations frequented (bar A, bar B, hotel, train station, library).	80% cases spent time at location other than shelter while contagious 71% Bar A, 59% Train station, 53% Library, 35% Bar B Infectious period <i>M</i> = 162 days LOS at shelter <i>OR</i> 2.9 Smoked >1yr <i>OR</i> 8.5 (94%) Excess ETOH <i>OR</i> 4.2 (82%) Frequented bar <i>OR</i> 3.7	Despite national ↓of TB, homeless still vulnerable Risk factors for getting TB: living at shelter, smoking, excessive ETOH Transmission of TB from homeless can affect the general population <u>Limitation:</u> Small sample may not provide adequate odds ratio data. Selection bias can affect results
Evaluation of CI for identified homeless TB cases (Yun et al., 2003)	Retrospective data review from data obtained from Reichler et al. 2002 study for homeless cases only Homeless: self report up to 1 year from DX and anyone living at	Focus on contact investigations done in 1996 of TB cases >15 y.o. 11 health depts applied, 5 incl Homeless residing in shelters vs not	Number of contacts identified, fully screened and infected for homeless sheltered compared to those not in shelter Type and completeness of data collected	26% homeless had no contacts vs. 12% non-homeless ↑contacts those in shelters than homeless not in shelters No association in smear + and smear – contacts (<i>p</i> =	Study showed differences in CI between homeless sheltered and not sheltered Development of electronic database improve analysis <u>Limitations:</u> rely solely on documentation which may be

Purpose (source)	Design, Key Variables	Sample/ Setting	Measures	Findings	Author Conclusions, Limitations
	shelter at time of DX	living in shelters		.5)	incomplete, data sample small; Older study yet most recent in this topic
	Homeless vs non-homeless case data from Reichler et al. 2002 study	27 identified as homeless out of 349 cases; 12 shelter residents and 15 not in shelters but HX of homelessness within past year		62% contacts completed screening, 18% never evaluated	
		479 contacts from 20 homeless cases		No significant difference in TX completion (shelter vs non-sheltered) or smear + / smear – 61 started; 44% completed	
Using QFT in field CI in congregate settings (Trieu, Proops and Ahuja, 2013)	2 NYC CI that used QFT in the field 1 st case: 2 residential hotels 2 nd case: 1 worksite	42 contacts to 2 TB cases 35 foreign born	Advantages, limitations & feasibility of using QFT in the field	Limitations of QFT were cost and training (phlebotomy) Benefits- single encounter, high completion, fewer false positives	QFT in the field is feasible.
Estimate outcomes and effectiveness and identify gaps of CI in California (Springson et al., 2003)	Retrospective study Data abstraction ARPE tool submitted to CADPH DV: Cost and effectiveness of CI IV: CI reporting	California July 1, 1999- June 30, 2000 2,032 TB cases reported 17,774 contacts 62% smear + 38% smear – No other	ARPE tool- includes info on 9 variables and 2 categories of TB cases Categories TB cases: smear +/-culture + smear -/culture + Variables: Contact elicitation >1, Contact evaluation, TB disease, LTBI, LTBI started TX, LTBI	CA met 1 of the 6 CDC and state objectives for CI 11% no contacts, 3 x as many contacts elicited for smear + than smear – Average contacts per case Smear + 10.5 Smear – 5.8 Contact evaluation 87.7% LTBI TX completion	California reports 20% of yearly US TB cases, second highest contacts at greatest risk of developing TB need to be prioritized, LTBI TX needs to be completed Despite 92% rate of identifying contacts, 214 had zero contacts. <u>Limitations:</u> Length of study only 1 year,

Purpose (source)	Design, Key Variables	Sample/ Setting	Measures	Findings	Author Conclusions, Limitations
		demographics provided	completed TX Cost for CI estimated based on methods from another study and based on 1998 costs: Drug sensitive: \$2,263 MDR: \$7,329	64.2% CI identified 81% TB cases CI prevented 34.6% of expected future TB cases 1 Finding exceeding CA and CDC outcomes: 92% smear + cases at least 1 contact identified	Older, current data still shows CA as top leading reporter of TB cases in U.S. ARPE captures only 9 variables not enough to provide information (why low completion rates)
Evaluate CI and outcomes throughout US (Reichler et al., 2002)	Retrospective study Health depts. had to meet 3 standards to qualify for study: 1. Have a CI policy for TB 2. Written records for TB case & CI 3. Reported 50 or more TB pts annually DV: Completeness of CI documentation IV: CI documentation	Focus on contact investigations done in 1996 of TB cases >15 y.o. 11 health depts applied, 5 accepted 360 patient charts reviewed, 11 excluded- total 349; 54% smear + 38% smear - 52% black, 21% white, 13% Asian, 12% Hispanic 67% men, 33% women	Data abstraction from charts Number of contacts identified, fully screened and infected per TB case Rates of TB infection and disease in contacts Type and completeness of data collected	3,824 contacts for all 349 cases. 13% cases 0 contacts Patients with no contacts more likely live in homeless shelter, $p < .001$ 50% homeless cases contacts, 55% complete screenings Contacts more likely have complete screening, $p < .001$, if they were: < 15 y.o (76% screened) or exposed to + smear case (74% screened) Contacts exposed to + smear and + cavitory more likely to be infected $p < .001$ (62%)	Improvement needed in CI to identify and fully screen contacts to TB case Identifying predetermined # of contacts not useful; but each case should have at least 1 contact Written documentation is key, including characteristics to identify high risk characteristics for TB <u>Limitations:</u> selection bias, no randomization Retrospective study- Older. CI guidelines have changed but findings still applicable

Note. LTBI = latent Tuberculosis Infection; DV = dependent variable; IV = independent variable; LA = Los Angeles; INH = Isoniazid; DOT = directly observed therapy; DX = diagnosis; TB = tuberculosis; y.o. = years old; nsg = nursing; CDC = Centers for Disease Control; CI = contact investigation; CADPH = California Department of Public Health; MDR = multi-drug resistant; CA = California; depts. = departments, incl = included; HX = history, US = United States; ARPE = Aggregated reports for tuberculosis program evaluation; LOS = length of stay; ETOH = alcohol; OR = odds ratio; SX = symptoms; TX = treatment; HIV = Human Immunodeficiency Virus; QFT = quantiferon; NYC = New York City; pts = patients; Aug = August; neg = negative; yr = year; vs = versus;

Table 3. Cost Analysis for IGRA and TST

Purpose (source)	Design, Key Variables	Sample/ Setting	Measures	Findings	Author Conclusions, Limitations
Cost analysis of QFT vs TST in U.S. & foreign born in PH clinic False pos models for US and foreign born. (Iqbal et al., 2013)	Comparative cost analysis Used two excel calculators (one for US born, one for foreign born) Prevalence rate LTBI CDC stats- US born 2%; foreign born 19%	PH clinic (St Louis, Missouri) Used eMR data from clinic for pts in 2007 > 18y.o. +TST, neg XRAY, TX with INH only.	<u>Screening</u> - test, 10min staff time <u>XRAY</u> - cost of xray, 10 min radiologist, 15 min radiology tech time <u>TX</u> - 9 mos INH 300mg, B6 50mg <u>Administrative</u> - 10 min staff time, 10 min MD, LFT	TST (2 visits) total \$38 QFT (1 visit) total \$74 XRAY- total \$82 TX- total \$351 (9 month) Administrative- total \$144 (9 month) US born- false pos: TST-66%; QFT 40% Foreign born- false pos: TST-69%; QFT 18%	For US born screening and TX (assumed 1,000 pts) cost was lower when using TST (\$63,388) compared to QFT (\$88,425) For Foreign born screening and TX (assumed 1,000 pts) cost was lower when using QFT (\$177,860) compared to TST (\$313,806)
Cost & health impacts in targeted LTBI testing in U.S. (Miller et al., 2006)	Cost comparison of state law mandated TB screening with jail inmates vs non mandated outreach to homeless Cost, morbidity, treatment & disease averted TST placement LTBI treatment	Retrospective analysis and modeling homeless, jail inmates Study period jail: 12/19/2001 - 12/18/2002 Study period homeless: CY 2003	incidence, prevalence & cases averted. Sums of screening cost plus treatment cost compared Used Medicare national average allowance & mean fee for non-Medicare charges & average wholesale price for drugs	Jail: 22,920 inmates screened; Found 7 TB cases out of 14 suspects; 211 prescribed LTBI TX Outreach: 822 screened; 10 TB cases out of 34 suspects; 181 prescribed LTBI TX Jail found fewer TB cases than targeted outreach	Use risk based not population based screening. Target testing was more efficient than mandate testing. Limitations: no cost analysis for contact investigation; used TST only
Cost effectiveness of IGRA in screening for TB in prisons in developed countries	Cost effectiveness using Markov models looking at QALYs Looked at cost for : healthy; LTBI; TB and	Prisoners aged 20 and older in Japan Placed in 1 of 4 cohorts: base case, HIV, MDR,	Cost for QFT included screening kits, one MD visit, cost for lab tech Cost for TST included 2 MD visits, TST reagent	QFT (\$1,477) more cost effective than TST (\$1,890) in the following categories: Base Case, HIV, MDR and HIV and MDR	QFT most effective method for screening in prisons in developed countries. QFT provided superior cost effectiveness likely due to ↑

Purpose (source)	Design, Key Variables	Sample/ Setting	Measures	Findings	Author Conclusions, Limitations
(Kowada, A., 2013)	death Cost, incremental cost, effectiveness (QALY), incremental effectiveness, ICER	HIV and MDR 4 strategies: QFT only TST only TST followed by QFT CXR only	Cost for CXR included material cost, one MD visit and rad tech Cost LTBI based on published literature		specificity of QFT compared to TST & CXR alone.
Feasibility, acceptability and cost of IGRA (Dewan et al., 2006)	Medical records review for IGRA results & completion of diagnostic eval	SF health dept, 6 community clinics with high pt population of homeless, immigrant & IDU from 11/2003 to 2/2005 Excluded <17 y.o., HIV or PG 4,143 evaluated;	Data collected as part of daily routine procedures Feasibility of IGRA measured by: (a) valid IGRA (b) completion of screening Acceptability measured by phlebotomy refusal Cost- clinical & lab; Reviewed TB screening log for IGRA refusal & phlebotomy failure	225 (5%) specimens not tested. 92% IGRA results 89 (2%) indeterminate 819 + IGRA and 64% completed diagnostic evaluation within 30 days. Refusals by patient for IGRA was 5% and failed IGRA was 8% IGRA cost \$33.67 per patient	Results from 1.5 years post IGRA implementation Use of IGRA was feasible among homeless, IDU and immigrant patients in SF Use of IGRA increases completion rates of diagnostic evaluation for LTBI Limitation- not RCT
Systematic review of cost of TB screening (Nienhaus, Schablon, Costa & Diel, 2011)	Systematic review of cost of IGRA and TST	Medline & Embase searched May 2011 75 studies found, 13 original studies 2 studies used TSPOT; 11 used QFT	Markov modeling looking at QALYs, LFY and ICER Progression rate Specificity, sensitivity Cost of IGRA	Variability of percentages used for specificity and sensitivity when calculating cost effectiveness Cost of TST and IGRA varied and could not be compared	All 13 studies found decreased cost when using IGRA Strong evidence in using IGRA to screen high risk groups Limitations: lack of definition for cost effectiveness leads to multiple variables unable to compare

Purpose (source)	Design, Key Variables	Sample/ Setting	Measures	Findings	Author Conclusions, Limitations
				Too many differing variables to compare studies	

Note. QFT = quantiferon; TST = tuberculin skin test; PH = public health; LTBI = latent tuberculosis infection; CDC = centers for disease control; eMR = electronic medical record; TX = treatment; INH = isoniazid; MD = medical doctor; LFT = liver function test; pt = patients; y.o. = years old; pts = patients; U.S. = United States; TB = tuberculosis; CY = calendar year; QALYs = quality adjusted life years; IGRA = interferon gamma release assay; CXR = chest x ray; ICER = incremental cost effectiveness ratio; dept = department; HIV = Human Immunodeficiency Virus; PG = pregnant; SF = San Francisco; IDU = Intravenous drug user; RCT = randomized control trial; LYG = life years gained; MDR = multi drug resistant; pos = positive; neg = negative; min = minutes; mos = months; mg = milligrams; tech = technician; vs = versus; eval = evaluation.

